

The cash flow activities and budgeting process of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City: Basis for budgeting strategies

Arline A. Mandigma, Jhona Mae A. Guico, Jinky C. Mas, Janelle A. Ramirez, Ivan C. Suarez, Robert John R. Perez

Abstract

Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are recognized as the Philippines' economic lifeblood, which must prioritize financial planning by considering a budget a tool for efficient financial planning and management. Thus, researchers were prompted to determine microbusinesses' cash flow activities and budgeting processes in Batangas City to develop budgeting strategies. The descriptive-quantitative research approach was used, and self-constructed questionnaires were responded to by 204 microbusinesses consisting of 14 bakeries and 190 sari-sari stores. Findings revealed that most microbusinesses in Batangas City have no employees and have been operating for about five years and below, with capitalization amounting to P500,000 and below. Microbusinesses often practiced cash flow activities such as operating and investing activities and practiced financing activities sometimes. The budgeting process of microbusinesses, including budget preparation, budget approval, and budget evaluation, were slightly practiced, and budget execution was the one that needed to be practiced. There is a significant relationship between microbusinesses' cash flow activities and budgeting. In operating activity, budget preparation, budget approval, budget execution, and budget evaluation are associated with this positively. When grouped according to profile, cash flow activities, such as operating and investing activities, had a significant difference, while financing activities had none. When grouped according to the number of employees in the budgeting process, there is no significant difference except in budget approval. When grouped according to years of operation, the budgeting process is the same except in budget evaluation. However, there is no significant difference in all phases of the budgeting process when grouped according to capitalization. The budgeting strategies aim to develop microbusinesses' cash flow activities and budgeting process. The researchers are motivated to develop budgeting strategies to help microbusiness owners be knowledgeable and educated on the budgeting process and cash flow activities.

Keywords: Budgeting process; budgeting strategies; cash flow; microbusiness.

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Introduction

A firm's economy is its lifeblood, and business organizations must emphasize financial planning by collecting money and spending it prudently. A budget is a financial planning and management tool. A well-integrated budget process with other activities, such as planning and management, leads to better financial and program decisions, which lead to improved operations. Budgets are essential to a company's success and important for strategic planning since they provide management with key information for obtaining desired goals. It also assists an organization in ensuring that its financial resources are utilized appropriately and efficiently.

Poor financial management, such as failing to use budgets for planning and control, typically leads to poor economic performance and company failure. In the United States, nearly 390,000 businesses collapsed in 2014 (Foster, 2017), with inadequate planning leading to most bankruptcies. Poor financial management, especially the inability to use budgets for planning and control, is a significant cause of failure in small businesses (Karadag, 2015). Considering that financial management is the heart of a small business's entire management system, ineffectiveness and inefficiencies in financial management harm a small and medium-sized enterprise's (SME) lifespan and performance.

Micro, small, and medium-sized businesses are widely seen as fueling a country's economic development and advancing the prospects for proper growth. More than 90 percent of the firms in the Philippines fall into the category of micro, small, or medium firms, which provide the majority of job possibilities and the majority of industrial and economic activity. Because of the expanding population of these types of businesses in the Philippines, their goods are vital to the degree that they offer people's daily necessities by satisfying their needs as soon as they are needed. They also generate jobs by hiring workers, which helps to lessen the country's unemployment rate. However, because of the current COVID-19 pandemic, like other businesses on a national, regional, and worldwide scale, micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) also suffered massive losses, a severe decline in demand, falling income, layoffs, and even the closure of several company divisions.

Among these enterprises, microbusinesses were the main focus of the study. According to Burton (2013), microbusinesses (companies with fewer than ten employees) are a common and vital part of today's economy. The specific business problem is that some small business leaders need to know to what extent, if any, budget planning, budget control, and the age of the business predict financial performance. Furthermore, it is concluded that strategic planning favorably affects the performance of MSMEs. However, little attention is paid to investigating MSMEs' budgeting processes, making it an undeveloped study topic that needs further attention. Firms' budgeting processes vary based on their size and organizational variety.

The researchers, being accounting students, believe that budgeting is one of the foundations of a business's success. The researchers noticed that the primary research done so far has been mainly focused on government budgeting and large companies' budgeting, leaving a gap in microbusiness budgeting. Ergo, the objective of the study is to determine the budgeting process and cash flow activities of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City, which serve as the basis for budgeting strategies. Browsing different dissertations and journals online, researchers have not seen any related literature about budgeting in Batangas City. This inspired the researchers to conduct this study, and they chose Batangas City as the area to be studied. To go on with it further, despite the unavailability of studies about it in Batangas City, researchers conducted pre-interviews among selected micro-business owners. They discovered a genuinely existing problem in that area, saying microbusinesses need to perform a proper budgeting process. They are just budgeting utilizing actual thinking without any documents or papers required.

According to Roddy (2022), half of the small businesses (50%) did not create an official, formally documented budget in 2020, which suggests that some business owners see budgets as an unnecessary structure. This study was conducted because one of the most significant issues some microbusinesses face is their belief that a budget is unnecessary. Some of them fail to have adequate knowledge about the budgeting process, which tends to cause their businesses to not be profitable at their peak. The eagerness of the researchers to help and assist microbusiness owners in being knowledgeable and educated on the budgeting process in terms of budget preparation, budget approval, budget execution, and budget evaluation motivated them to pursue this study.

This study is supported by the theory of Rajan et al. (2016), who posited that a standard budget process incorporates four distinct stages: Budget definition and Formulation, Budget negotiation and approval, Budget execution, and Budget Evaluation. Budget definition and formulation convert policy objectives into cost estimates that fit within the sector's proposed budget limitations. The budget negotiation and approval process culminates in the formation of a formal proposal to reflect income and spending projections for the budget period (usually a year). Budget execution, often known as expenditure, is a series of procedures that result in efficient fund transfers from the treasury to the firm. Budget evaluation includes internal and external control methods that verify compliance with set objectives and processes. Lastly, another theory that supports this study is the accounting standard PAS 7, which talks about cash flow activities. As stated in the book of Valix et al. (2020), cash flow activities are classified as operating, investing, and financing activities. Operating activities are the cash flows mainly generated by the entity's primary revenue-generating activities. Investing activities are generated by purchasing and selling long-term assets and other investments not included in the cash equivalent, and financing activities are generated by the entity's equity capital and borrowings.

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To determine the profile of microbusinesses in Batangas City regarding the number of employees, years of operation, and capitalization as of 2021.
2. To describe how frequently microbusinesses practice cash flow activities in operating, investing, and financing activities.
3. To ascertain how microbusinesses respond in the budgeting process in terms of budget preparation, budget approval, budget execution, and budget evaluation.
4. To investigate the significant relationship between microbusinesses' cash flow activities and the budgeting process.
5. To look into the significant difference in cash flow activities and the budgeting process when grouped according to profile variables.
6. To propose budgeting strategies based on the analysis.

Methodology

The study used a descriptive correctional causal design to describe the characteristics of respondents' microbusinesses, such as the number of employees, years of operation, and capitalization as of 2021, and determine whether there is a relationship between the budgeting process and cash flow activities. As stated, descriptive correlational design is a type of research where the researcher examines the strength of the relationship between two or more variables.

The study's total population is one thousand ninety-one (1,091) registered microbusiness owners in Batangas City, based on the 2021 List of Registered Microbusiness Establishments. It comprises one thousand twenty (1,020) Sari-sari store owners and seventy-one (71) Bakeshop owners. The researchers did an automatic calculation using a Raosoft calculator; only two hundred eighty-five (285) microbusinesses were involved in the study. Out of 285 target respondents, only 204, or 72%, participated. Specifically, the respondents are composed of 190 sari-sari store businesses and 14 bakeries. Moreover, the researchers used purposive sampling and handpicked the respondents to be included in the sample. Respondents who participated in the study were chosen based on the researchers' judgment.

The researchers used a self-constructed questionnaire as the main instrument to assemble and gather the essential information needed for the study. A dry run and reliability test were conducted, and they resulted in a 0.937 using Cronbach's Alpha, interpreted as excellent internal consistency. The questionnaire was administered in Google Forms for respondents with social media accounts. At the same time, researchers also utilized a hard copy of the questionnaires for those respondents who could not be reached online. A letter to the respondents was attached to the questionnaire, including informed consent and disclosing that answering the questionnaire is voluntary and in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The researchers submitted a letter to Batangas City government officials for assistance in obtaining an updated microbusiness list. A letter to the respondents is included with the questionnaire, assuring them that the information they provide will be kept secret and used solely for academic and research purposes.

Researchers visited the workplaces of microbusiness owners to distribute questionnaires and sought the help of their acquaintances who have connections and know registered microbusiness owners in their neighborhood to easily gather the data needed. The statistical treatments applied were the frequency and percentage for the statement of the problem 1, weighted mean, and composite mean to answer the statements of the problems 2 and 3, Spearman rho to address the statement of the problem 4, and compare means for the statement of the problem 5. After data gathering, the results were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Results and Discussion

Profile of Microbusinesses in Batangas City

Table 1. Number of employees

Number of employees	Frequency	Percentage
None	139	68.14
One to Two	50	24.51
Three to Four	9	4.41
Five to Six	1	0.49
Seven to Nine	5	2.45
Total	204	100.00

Most of the respondents had no employees, representing 68.14 percent of the total respondents. 24.51 percent have one to two employees, and the lowest number of respondents are those with five to six employees. It implies that microbusinesses are mostly owned by sole proprietors who run and operate the business. Murray (2020) states that sole proprietorships with no employees are also included in certain definitions of microbusinesses.

Table 2. Years in operation

Years in operation	Frequency	Percentage
5 years and below	116	56.86
More than 5 years but less than 10 years	45	22.06
More than 10 years but less than 15 years	26	12.75
More than 15 years but less than 20 years	5	2.45
More than 20 years but less than 25 years	6	2.94
More than 25 years	6	2.94
Total	204	100.00

One hundred sixteen (116), or 56.86 percent, of the respondents operate between 5 and below, which is the highest rank. Next is the business operation ranging from more than 5 years to less than 10 years, with 45 respondents, equivalent to 22.06 percent. The lowest number of respondents is more than 15 years in operation, consisting of 2.45 percent.

Looking at their years of operation, it can be said that the majority are still in the early stages of their existence. It was supported by the study of Anoo et al. (2020), which claimed that start-up businesses required government assistance for business sustainability and continuity.

Table 3. Capitalization as of 2021

Capitalization	Frequency	Percentage
Below P500,000	189	92.65
P 500,001 to P1,000,000	10	4.90
P1,000,001 to P1,500,000	4	1.96
P1,500,001 to P2,000,000	0	0.00
P2,000,001 to P2,500,000	0	0.00
P2,500,001 to P3,000,000	1	0.49
Total	204	100.00

The majority of the respondents were below P500,000 in their capital, comprising 92.65 percent, or one hundred eighty-nine of the total respondents. Ten of the respondents, or 4.90 percent, had P500,001 to P1,000,000 in their capital. Meanwhile, no one has a capitalization of P1,500,001 to P2,000,000 or P2,000,001 to P2,500,000.

It implies that microbusinesses have limited sources of capital since they are managed by only one person. Gross (2022) emphasises that microbusinesses are typically managed by solopreneurs, freelancers, and side hustlers who start a business with few operational and capital requirements.

Cash Flow Activities of Microbusinesses in Batangas City

This study looked into the cash flow of a few microbusinesses in Batangas City. Cash flow activities are a type of business activity that deals with how microbusinesses, notably sari-sari stores, manage their cash flow. It has three categories of activities: operating, investing, and financing.

Table 4. Cash flow as to operating activities of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City

Operating Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Recording cash from sale	2.01	Sometimes	4
2. Recording account receivables	3.30	Always	2
3. Paying salaries and wages to employees	1.76	Sometimes	5
4. Paying to suppliers	2.87	Often	3
5. Paying utilities expenses	3.64	Always	1
Composite Mean	2.72	Often	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Always; 2.51-3.25: Often; 1.76-2.50: Sometimes; 1.00-1.75: Seldom

Table 4 presents the cash flow as it relates to the operating activities of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City. Observing the responses of the microbusiness owners, they agreed from a sometimes to an always frequency when it comes to their cash flow as well as their operating activities, with a composite mean of 2.72 (Often). Specifically, microbusinesses are always paying utility expenses, making them at the top with a weighted mean of 3.64. Meanwhile, the item that garnered the lowest rating was that some microbusiness owners paid salaries and wages to employees, with a weighted mean of 1.76 and a verbal interpretation of sometimes.

It means that microbusinesses often perform operating activities such as paying expenses and keeping records. Accounting record-keeping is essential for making decisions and improving business efficiency and productivity for effective business performance. A study by Abdul-Rahamon and Adejare (2014) found that accounting record-keeping had an impact on the performance of small businesses.

Table 5. Cash flow as to investing activities of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City

Investing Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Purchasing equipment for business	2.99	Often	2
2. Paying loan advances to supplier	2.17	Sometimes	5
3. Paying for installation necessary equipment	2.46	Sometimes	3
4. Acquiring intangible assets	3.77	Always	1
5. Saving extra income in the bank	2.32	Sometimes	4
Composite Mean	2.74	Often	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Always; 2.51-3.25: Often; 1.76-2.50: Sometimes; 1.00-1.75: Seldom

Table 5 presents the cash flow from investing activities. When it comes to their cash flow and investing activities, the microbusiness owners agreed they often engaged in investing activities, with a composite mean of 2.74 (Often). Precisely, the highest weighted mean of 3.77 pertaining to acquiring intangible assets is the lone item that has the verbal interpretation of "Always". It denoted that those microbusinesses often invested in their businesses, acquiring pieces of equipment and intangible assets to benefit their operations. On the other side, the lowest mean is 2.17, with a verbal interpretation of sometimes.

Similarly, according to Omag (2016), money is typically invested in productive assets. Among the assets required for expansion may be property, plants, equipment, intangible assets, and long-term securities. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean is 2.17, which indicates that microbusinesses sometimes pay loan advances to suppliers.

Table 6. Cash flow as to financing activities of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City

Financing Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Repaying the borrowed money	3.11	Often	1
2. Borrowing money from financial institution	1.66	Seldom	5
3. Paying from improvement of property and equipment	2.39	Sometimes	3
4. Paying interest on debt loans	2.24	Sometimes	4
5. Using part of business income for personal use	2.90	Often	2
Composite Mean	2.46	Sometimes	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Always; 2.51-3.25: Often; 1.76-2.50: Sometimes; 1.00-1.75: Seldom

Table 6 presents cash flow as a means of financing the activities of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City. Microbusiness owners agreed that when it comes to their cash flow and financing activities, they perform them sometimes, with a composite mean of 2.46. The financing activity of repaying the borrowed money gains the highest spot with a weighted mean of 3.11 and an interpretation of often.

However, the lowest rank with a weighted mean of 1.66 and a verbal interpretation of rarely is borrowing money from financial institutions. They experienced difficulties in terms of borrowing because investors or banks checked the capital of the business. Yoshino and Taghizadeh-Hesary (2017) mentioned that borrowing money from banks is also tough for riskier small and medium enterprises. Banks find it difficult to evaluate it because they frequently lack effective accounting systems.

Budgeting Process of Selected Microbusinesses in Batangas City

The budgeting process of select microbusinesses in Batangas City was determined in this study. It involves formulating, implementing, and evaluating a budget that provides services and capital assets, particularly fixed resources such as money.

Table 7. Budget preparation of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City

Budget Preparation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Clearly state goals.	2.95	Moderately Practiced	1
2. Plan out precise measures based on the previous data.	1.53	Not Practiced	6
3. Outline the procedures that should be done in the budgeting process.	1.43	Not Practiced	7
4. Forecast future-benefits.	1.53	Not Practiced	6
5. Sort out what is achievable, and what will take some time to be part of a plan.	2.08	Slightly Practiced	5
6. Identify and incorporate essential resources of business.	2.84	Moderately Practiced	2
7. Calculate how much money will need to attain business goals.	2.36	Slightly Practiced	3
8. Estimate future revenue based on predicted expenses.	2.33	Slightly Practiced	4
Composite Mean	2.74	Slightly Practiced	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Highly Practiced; 2.51-3.25: Moderately Practiced; 1.76-2.50: Slightly Practiced; 1.00-1.75: Not Practiced

Table 7 presents the budget preparation of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City. It can be observed that the respondents were slightly practicing the budget process in terms of budget preparation, with a composite mean of 2.13. Some microbusinesses do not fully anticipate future income and costs, forecast some benefits, or plan to reach their objectives because they view it as time-consuming. Cardoso (2014) claims that budget preparation is expensive since it requires time and other resources. Some microbusinesses see budgeting as not so important as it requires time and other resources.

The item that was given the highest weighted mean is clearly stating goals with a weighted mean of 2.95. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean was 1.43, representing "outline the procedures that should be done in the budgeting process," which was verbally interpreted as not practiced.

Table 8. Budget approval of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City

Budget Approval	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Approving the orders before the delivery of the supplier	2.50	Slightly Practiced	2
2. Approving the made list of insufficiency in inventory by the employee	1.45	Not Practiced	6
3. Coordinating the budget with the employees to gain suggestions	1.46	Not Practiced	5
4. Presenting previous receipts when coordinating with employees for further understanding of the budget	1.66	Not Practiced	4
5. Ensuring that the employees are aware of the overall budget.	1.85	Slightly Practiced	3
6. Making the budget and approving it.	2.97	Moderately Practiced	1
Composite Mean	1.98	Slightly Practiced	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Highly Practiced; 2.51-3.25: Moderately Practiced; 1.76-2.50: Slightly Practiced; 1.00-1.75: Not Practiced

Table 8 presents the budget approval of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City. It can be observed that the respondents were slightly practicing the budget process in terms of budget approval, with a composite mean of 1.98. The item with the highest mean of 2.97, "making the budget and approving it", was verbally interpreted as moderately practiced. On the other hand, "approving the made list of insufficiency in inventory by the employee," being the lowest rank in terms of weighted mean with 1.45, is interpreted as not practiced.

It connoted that microbusinesses do budgets sometimes in the way of thinking and approving them once they are okay. As most of them were often managed by one owner, which means that they are handling the business and making the budget all on their own and have no need to coordinate it with others. According to Roddy (2022), half of the small businesses (50%) did not create an official, formally documented budget, which suggests that some business owners see budgets as an unnecessary structure. But other experts consider documented budgeting an essential business practice.

Table 9 presents the budget execution of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City. It can be observed that the respondents were not practicing the budget process in terms of budget execution, with a composite mean of 1.73. Microbusinesses do not pay so much attention to executing budgets and making them. Others see budgets as unnecessary structures in small firms with busy schedules that they will solely manage. In the study of Johansson (2014), it is said that significant time and effort are invested into establishing a budget that becomes overly comprehensive. Paying debt on time has the highest weighted mean of 2.80 and is verbally interpreted as moderately practiced. Further, the lowest weighted mean was 1.41, which denotes that microbusinesses do not enforce or apply limitations and conditions set in the budget, as interpreted as not being practiced.

Table 9. Budget execution of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City

Budget Execution	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Put certain strategies in action.	1.46	Not Practiced	7
2. Follow the set procedures in achieving financial goals.	1.51	Not Practiced	6
3. Pay the debt on time.	2.80	Moderately Practiced	1
4. Put in place budget rules that will help in times of difficulty.	1.58	Not Practiced	4
5. Align the budget with the capital plan/spending.	1.67	Not Practiced	3
6. Enforce or apply limitations and conditions that are set in the budget.	1.41	Not Practiced	8
7. Institute best budgeting practices if necessary.	1.56	Not Practiced	5
8. Find ways to solve issues immediately that arise during implementation.	1.87	Slightly Practiced	2
Composite Mean	1.73	Not Practiced	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Highly Practiced; 2.51-3.25: Moderately Practiced; 1.76-2.50: Slightly Practiced; 1.00-1.75: Not Practiced

Table 10. Budget evaluation of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City

Budget Evaluation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Keep track of and assess financial progress.	3.08	Moderately Practiced	1
2. Monitoring through comparing actual spending and spending plans.	1.54	Not Practiced	4
3. Investigate differences between actual budget and budgeted performance.	1.53	Not Practiced	5
4. Secure compliance with the spending restrictions.	2.63	Moderately Practiced	2
5. Analyze changes in the internal and external environment during monitor and make adjustment accordingly.	2.42	Slightly Practiced	3
6. Develop a plan of corrective action to narrow the gap between the expected and actual budget.	1.36	Not Practiced	7
7. Collect and record relevant information to assist in future budget preparation.	1.35	Not Practiced	8
8. Revise the budget after the corrective actions.	1.42	Not Practiced	6
Composite Mean	1.92	Slightly Practiced	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Highly Practiced; 2.51-3.25: Moderately Practiced; 1.76-2.50: Slightly Practiced; 1.00-1.75: Not Practiced

Table 10 presents the budget evaluation of selected microbusinesses in Batangas City. It can be observed that the respondents were slightly practicing the budget process in terms of budget evaluation, with a composite mean of 1.92. Microbusinesses often evaluate budgets. They seldom monitor every financial transaction and keep track of it. Having the indication for preparing budgets as slightly practiced, it makes sense that microbusinesses have some budget to be evaluated. This evaluation involves monitoring, observing, and controlling their corresponding decisive plans.

Akande and Oluwaseun (2014) concede that budgeting identifies areas where actual performance differs from anticipated performance, allowing for necessary corrective action (as cited in Nso, 2020). Keeping track of and assessing financial progress has the highest weighted mean of 3.08, which is interpreted as moderately practiced. On the contrary, collecting and recording relevant information to assist in future budget preparation is the activity that got the lowest weighted mean of 1.35 under budget evaluation.

Relationship between microbusinesses' cash flow activities and the budgeting process

Table 11. Relationship between operating activities and budgeting process

Budgeting Process	Significance Level	Computed Values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Budget Preparation	0.000	0.364	Reject	Significant
Budget Approval	0.000	0.548	Reject	Significant
Budget Execution	0.000	0.373	Reject	Significant
Budget Evaluation	0.006	0.193	Reject	Significant

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

The relationship between operating activities and budgeting processes has a significant level of 0.000, while budget evaluation has a significant level of 0.006. Thus, there was a significant relationship between operating activities and the budgeting process. The computed values of 0.364, 0.548, 0.373, and 0.193 imply that there was a strong correlation. Accordingly, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 12. Relationship between investing activities and budgeting process

Budgeting Process	Significance Level	Computed Values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Budget Preparation	0.000	0.296	Reject	Significant
Budget Approval	0.000	0.491	Reject	Significant
Budget Execution	0.000	0.301	Reject	Significant
Budget Evaluation	0.000	0.324	Reject	Significant

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

Investing activities and the budgeting process have a significant relationship with each other. The table shows that investing activities and budgeting processes derived a significant level of 0.000. In this case, there was a significant relationship between investing activities and the budgeting process. The computed values of 0.296, 0.491, 0.301, and 0.324, respectively, indicate a strong correlation. In this way, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Financing activities and budgeting processes yielded a significant level of 0.000. In this case, there was a significant relationship between investing activities and the budgeting process. The computed values of 0.277, 0.333, 0.364, and 0.152, respectively, indicate a strong correlation. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected. It shows that financing activities have a significant relationship with the budgeting process.

Table 13. Relationship between financing activities and budgeting process

Budgeting Process	Significance Level	Computed Values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Budget Preparation	0.000	0.277	Reject	Significant
Budget Approval	0.000	0.333	Reject	Significant
Budget Execution	0.000	0.364	Reject	Significant
Budget Evaluation	0.030	0.152	Reject	Significant

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

Differences in cash flow activities and the budgeting process when grouped according to profile variables

Table 14. Significant difference in cash flow activities when grouped according to number of employees

Cash Flow	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
OA_ALL	29.182	0.000	Significant	Reject
IA_ALL	3.755	0.006	Significant	Reject
FA_ALL	0.737	0.568	Insignificant	Fail To Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

With computed values of 29.182 and a significance level of 0.000, it was concluded that there is a significant difference between operating activities and the number of employees. Garnering a computed value of 3.755 and a significant level of 0.006, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between investing activities and the number of employees was rejected. However, in terms of financing activities, it conceded a computed value of 0.737 and a significance level of 0.568. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. It implied that the operating and investing activities of microbusinesses were different from each other based on their number of employees.

Table 15. Significant difference in cash flow activities when grouped according to years in operation

Cash Flow	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
OA_ALL	8.404	0.000	Significant	Reject
IA_ALL	3.198	0.008	Significant	Reject
FA_ALL	1.296	0.267	Insignificant	Fail To Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

There is a significant difference between operating activities and years of operation, as the null hypothesis was rejected with a computed value of 8.404 and a significance level of 0.000. There is a significant difference between investing activities and years of operation, with a computed value of 3.198 and a significance level of 0.008, rejecting the null hypothesis as well. Meanwhile, it disclosed a computed value of 1.296 and a significance level of 0.267. Based on years of operation, financing activities do not differ significantly.

Table 16. Significant difference in cash flow activities when grouped according to capitalization

Cash Flow	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
OA_ALL	7.127	0.000	Significant	Reject
IA_ALL	3.883	0.010	Significant	Reject
FA_ALL	0.425	0.735	Insignificant	Fail To Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

With a computed value of 7.127 and a significance level of 0.000, it implies that there is a significant difference between operating activities and capitalization. It is also evident in investing activities, with a computed value of 3.883 and a significance level of 0.010, that there is a significant difference between them and capitalization. The result shows an insignificant relationship between financing activities and their capitalization, with a computed value of 0.425 and a significance level of 0.735. Microbusinesses respond differently in operational and investment activities when classified according to capitalization, but not in financing operations.

Table 17. Significant difference in budgeting process when grouped according to number of employees

Budgeting Process	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
BP_ALL	0.851	0.494	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BA_ALL	10.433	0.000	Significant	Reject
BE_ALL	0.697	0.595	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BEV_ALL	0.596	0.666	Insignificant	Fail To Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

Table 17 shows the computed values of 0.851, 0.697, and 0.596 that assume that there is no significant difference between budget preparation, execution, and evaluation and the number of employees. Thus, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. On the other hand, when it comes to budget approval, with a computed value of 10.433 and a significance level of 0.000, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 18. Significant difference in budgeting process when grouped according to years of operation

Budgeting Process	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
BP_ALL	0.457	0.808	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BA_ALL	1.868	0.102	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BE_ALL	0.567	0.725	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BEV_ALL	3.048	0.029	Significant	Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

However, despite their years of operation, microbusinesses engaged in the same budgeting process, with the exception of budget evaluation. The results showed a computed value of 0.457 and a significance level of 0.808 in budget preparation, indicating that the null hypothesis failed to be rejected.

Besides, budget approval gained a computed value of 1.868 and a significance value of 0.102; the null hypothesis was rejected. With a computed value of 0.567 and a significance level of 0.725, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. A computed value of 3.048 and a significance value of 0.029 were earned in the budget evaluation, so the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 19 showed a computed value of 1.917 and a significance level of 0.128, which means not rejecting the null hypothesis. However, budget approval has no significant difference based on capitalization, with a computed value of 1.244 and a significance value of 0.295. As per budget approval, with a computed value of 1.281 and a significance level of 0.282, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected. Lastly, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected since budget evaluation earned a computed value of 0.191 and a significance level of 0.903. Thus, there is no significant difference in the budgeting process when grouped according to capitalization.

Table 19. Significant difference in budgeting process when grouped according to years of capitalization

Budgeting Process	Computed Values	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
BP_ALL	1.917	0.128	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BA_ALL	1.244	0.295	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BE_ALL	1.281	0.282	Insignificant	Fail To Reject
BEV_ALL	0.191	0.903	Insignificant	Fail To Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05 Significance Level; Not Significant – More than 0.05 Significance Level

Proposed Budgeting Strategies

Rationale

Budgeting is the basis for all business success—a powerful tool that can affect the performance of an entire entity as a defensive stance against failure. As a systematic method of allocating financial, physical, and human resources to achieve organizational goals, microbusinesses must refer to a good budgeting process that will monitor the progress towards the goals, assist in the control of spending, and help predict cash flow for the organization (Akhilesh, 2014). The proposed budgeting strategies' execution time will be based on the calendar year as assumed by the researchers. Having flexible forecasting for complex spending and revenue goals allows the business to ensure business growth and development.

Basic Premises of the Strategies

The proposed budgeting strategies are based on the following premises:

1. The proposed budgeting strategies enhance the budgeting process of microbusinesses in terms of preparation, approval, execution, and evaluation of budgets. Also, it expounds on the efficiency of handling cash flow activities.
2. The enhancement of any microbusinesses' budgeting strategies lies on themselves, the employees (if any), the external factors, and their commitment and collective effort.
3. The proposed strategies are formulated to be deemed applicable to microbusinesses.

- The proposed strategies are based on the study's findings relative to the current budgeting strategies of microbusinesses. Some of their budgeting processes are practiced slightly, and many of these still need to be practiced. These all must be done effectively and must be open to any improvement.

Objectives of the Budgeting Strategies

Making a budget is an essential pillar of overall success and security. It enables monitoring and a better understanding of whether the company's revenue (incoming money) is sufficient to cover its expenses. These budgeting strategies aim to help microbusinesses become knowledgeable and educated about the budgeting process. It will also aid them with strategies to manage their cash flow activities like operating, investing, and financing efficiently and effectively to arrive at the desired results for the entity. The specific objectives of the budgeting strategies are:

- To effectively apply the budgeting process among microbusiness through gained knowledge that serves as a guide to achieving goals.
- To ensure and help increase the effectiveness and efficiency of budget preparation, approval, execution, and evaluation process of microbusinesses consistent with the entity's mission.
- To effectively ensure the efficient tracking and monitoring of the budget, or the money itself.

Concluding Statement

A key component of total success and security is budget creation. It enables monitoring and comprehending if the company generates enough income (incoming money) to cover its costs. Making better financial decisions with the aid of a budget is possible. A budget ensures that spending is under control and that savings are progressing as planned. Setting long-term financial objectives, avoiding overspending, breaking destructive spending patterns, and other things may all be done with a budget. These exact reasons indicate why budgeting is crucial for large companies, but even for small and microbusinesses. Budgeting is for all and will definitely bring success, growth, and development.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Majority of the microbusiness owners had no workers, operating for less than five (5) years, and with a capital of less than P500,000. Cash flow activities of microbusinesses including operating and investing activities were practiced often, while financing activities were practiced sometimes. Budgeting process of microbusinesses, including budget preparation, approval, and evaluation, are being practiced slightly since some microbusinesses are often run by one owner which means that they are handling the business and making the budget all on their own. They also view it as unnecessary, costly, and time-consuming since it requires time and other resources. Besides, budget execution was the one budgeting process that was not being practiced by microbusinesses, as they did not pay attention to executing their budgets.

There were strong significant relationships between cash flow activities like operating, investing, and financing activities and the budgeting process of microbusinesses such as budget preparation, budget approval, budget execution, and budget evaluation. There were significant differences in cash flow activities such as operating and investing activities when grouped according to profile while financing activities had no significant difference. In budgeting process, when grouped according to number of employees, there was no significant difference except in budget approval. Further, when grouped according to years of operation, there was no significant difference also in budgeting process except in budget evaluation. However, there was no significant difference in all phases of budgeting process when grouped according to capitalization. The proposed budgeting strategies were designed to improve microbusinesses' budgeting process and cash flow activities in Batangas City.

The following recommendations were developed based on the findings and conclusion:

- The proposed strategies may be endorsed to organizations, which are in the higher positions and supervising microbusinesses for future checking and validation and implement the proposed strategies since they have a contact to all registered microbusinesses in Batangas City.
- The proposed budgeting strategies may be distributed to the aspiring business owner and customers that they may use as a reference or guide to assist them enhance their budgeting skills before or after they start their business or in their personal finances.
- The output of the study may be used by the educational institutions since it can assist students and teachers develop better and more comprehensive decision-making skills and their knowledge of handling money.
- For future researchers, this paper may be replicated to cover more about microbusinesses and further continue the study. They may include the delimitations of the study such as other microbusinesses engaged in water refilling station, farm, and trading to be the respondents of the study, as well as their demographic profile.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Proposed Budget Plan

Objectives	Proposed Budgeting Strategy	Execution Time	How to Effectively Utilize?
BUDGET PREPARATION			
Plan out precise measures based on the previous data and outline the procedures that should be done in the budgeting process.	Outline the budget and projections, as guide in running the business.	Estimated Time: One and One-half (1 ½) month	Budget can help control the finances and track it. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track and categorize the expenses and calculate the net income. Set realistic goals and make a comprehensive plan. Adjust budget if necessary and review it regularly.
Forecast future benefits.	Be proactive instead of being reactive through forecasting.		Take into consideration events in the past and present, and then predict future wisely. Consider factors that may affect the business performance during its operation.
BUDGET APPROVAL			
Approving the made-list insufficiency in inventory by the employee, coordinating the budget and presenting previous receipts when coordinating with employees.	Have a participative budgeting process, involving employees in the budgeting.	Estimated Time: One (1) month	Note: Applicable to microbusiness with employees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involve people in the budgeting process. Let their voice be heard for suggestions and improvements and always be transparent.
BUDGET EXECUTION			
Put certain strategies into action and follow the set of procedures in achieving financial goals.	Translate strategies into specific actions, timeliness and responsibilities.	Estimated Time: Five to six (5-6) months	Strategies help define the business, give it a set of values and gives it purpose. Develop the business strategy through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have a clear vision. Be inspired to grow and expand Make fact-based decisions and make sure that strategies are achievable in short and long term.

Put in place budget rules that will help in times of difficulty and enforce or apply limitations and conditions that are set in the budget.	Have SMART goals: Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, Time-Bound.	It is easier to succeed when there are clearly defined objectives that are based in facts. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask what needs to be accomplished and steps need to be taken to achieve it.
Align the budget with the capital plan / spending or simply institute best budgeting strategy if necessary.	Allocate finances intelligently and strategize skillfully.	Finances are the lifeblood of the business, so, it must be put into consideration. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan ahead by assessing how much is needed for the bills. • Make sure to hold enough cash and cover the expenses.

BUDGET EVALUATION

Monitoring through comparing actual spending plans & investigate differences between actual budget and budgeted performance.	Gather past spending details and maintain frequent budget monitoring.	Estimated Time: Three and one half (3 ½) months	List what is earned, spent money on and owed. Try to look at enough bills and statements from past years to understand the usual earning and spending habits.
Collect and record relevant information to assist in the future budget preparation.	Have identified, accessed, and interpreted data and data sources.		Try to observe and collect past information and take corresponding actions if necessary.
Develop a plan of corrective actions to narrow the gap between the expected and actual budget or revise the budget after corrective action.	Projected budget is not always right. Have time to monitor it closely to enhance the budgeting process and achieve desired results.		Monitor frequently the budget. If strategic actions implemented are not effective, consider changing them.